

TOUGHNESS OF EPOXY POLYMERS CURED AT HIGH RATES

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1 Introduction

Epoxy polymers are used extensively in aerospace, automotive and electronics applications in the form of adhesives, surface coatings and advanced composite materials due to their outstanding mechanical and thermal properties. However, unmodified epoxy polymers exhibit brittle behaviour. The toughness of epoxies can be enhanced by the addition of nanoparticles. Soft rubber particles have been the most successful method to achieve ‘toughenability’ [1-2]. The manufacturing processes involved in the formation of toughened epoxies have great impact on the mechanical properties of the material and thermal processing can alter the effectiveness of the tougheners [3]. From a commercial point of view, minimizing the cure time by increasing the cure temperature and hence the cure rates of the epoxy systems will lead to a reduction in cost. However, when the cure cycle is accelerated to reduce manufacturing time and expense, the possibility of a runaway exotherm is increased which could result in the degradation and breakdown of the epoxy polymer. The fracture energy of epoxy polymers containing poly-siloxane core shell rubber (CSR) nanoparticles was studied in the current work. The effect of increasing the cure temperature on the measured fracture energy of the epoxy resin was also investigated.

2 Experimental

An amine-based cured diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) formed the basis of the different epoxy systems used in the current work. The resin formulation was altered by replacing 10 wt% of the DGEBA resin with a reactive diluent (HDDGE). Formulations containing 3%, 6% and 9% weight percentage of CSR were prepared and cured isothermally at 40°C, 50°C, 60°C and 70°C.

Single-edge notched bending (SENB) tests were performed to obtain the fracture energy, G_{IC} , in the opening mode according to the ASTM standard using the energy method approach. Scanning electron

microscopy (SEM) was used to validate the presence of voids and to determine their volume fraction on the fracture surface of SENB samples.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Fracture properties

A maximum fracture energy, G_{IC} , of $339 \pm 77 \text{ J/m}^2$ was measured for the unmodified epoxy polymer. The value was obtained at a cure temperature of 40°C. The addition of CSR nanoparticles to the polymer system increased this value significantly to $3920 \pm 140 \text{ J/m}^2$. This represents an increase in fracture energy of approximately 1000 % when the extent of CSR is increased from 0 wt% to 9 wt%. The cure rates and cure temperature do not alter the fracture energy and the fracture toughness for epoxy systems containing only a small amount of CSR (0 wt% and 3 wt%).

On the contrary from Figure 1, it is clear that when the amount of rubber particles is significant (6 wt% and 9 wt%), the temperature at which the sample is cured reduces the fracture properties of the material significantly. For example, the fracture energy of an epoxy system modified with 9 wt% of CSR cured at 40°C is $3920 \pm 140 \text{ J/m}^2$. This value drops to $2411 \pm 156 \text{ J/m}^2$ when the same formulation is cured at 70°C leading to a loss of toughness which is almost 40 %. Some synergetic effects were observed when the resin formulations were modified with the addition of silica nanoparticles.

3.2 Curing rate and toughness

The principal toughening mechanism associated with CSR nano-modified polymers [4] is plastic void growth of the matrix initiated by cavitation of the toughening particles. Plastic void growth can absorb a significant amount of energy and can be observed experimentally using a SEM. The fracture surface of a nanomodified epoxy systems containing 9 wt% of CSR nanoparticles cured at 40°C can be seen in

Figure 2. In the micrograph a well-dispersed microstructure of voids can be clearly observed. From Figure 3, it can be seen that a higher cure temperature, leads to some clustering and agglomeration of the particles which are no longer clearly distinguishable on the fracture surface. By comparing the different micro-graphs, it is possible to observe that when the rate of cure of the epoxy resin is increased, the dispersion of the CSR particles is affected. In the epoxy polymer with high content of CSR, the toughening additives interact with each-other, coalesce and as a result the voids observed on the fracture surface are not evenly distributed. Hence, the toughening effect of the CSR nanoparticles is inhibited since the growth of the voids surrounding these particles is limited by their surrounding space at the micro-structure of the material.

4 Conclusion

The addition of CSR nanoparticles to the epoxy matrix leads to a significant toughening of the polymer. For CSR nanomodified epoxies, the speed of cure is the decisive factor which determines the effectiveness of the preformed rubber particles.

When fast cure cycles are applied, the weight fraction of CSR nanoparticles is the principal indicator of the extent to which the increase in toughness of the epoxy polymer is inhibited. The higher the content of CSR particles, the greater the drop-in fracture energy observed experimentally.

3.3 Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Fracture energy versus curing temperature for CSR nanomodified epoxy systems.

Figure 2: SEM image of the fracture surface of an epoxy polymer cured at 40°C containing 9 wt% of CSR nanoparticles.

Figure 3: SEM image of the fracture surface of an epoxy polymer cured at 70°C containing 9 wt% of CSR nanoparticles.

3.3 References

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